

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B355
Date: 2 April 2008
Take Off: 10:56:03Z
Landing: 16:27:22
Flight Time 5h31m19s

Campaign: ADIENT

Operating Area: East Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chem	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Cloud physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Claire McConnell	University of Reading
9	AMS 1	James Allen	University of Manchester
10	AMS2	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
11	SP2	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester
12			
13			

Flight Track:

B355 Track 02-APR-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B355
 Date: 02 April 2008
 Project: ADIENT
 Location: East Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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103456		inu	0.04 kft	127	to nav
103505		gin	0.04 kft	127	on
103644		drs	0.04 kft	127	running
103932		horace	0.04 kft	127	40000/1500 recording
104801		ASP	0.04 kft	069	open
105603		T/O	0.03 kft	213	cranfield
105724		JW	2.1 kft	308	on
105734		nev	2.4 kft	306	on
105808		TW	4.1 kft	307	on - status red
105820		heiman	4.4 kft	313	open
111207		TW	15.0 kft	016	power cycled
111238		nev	15.0 kft	004	zero
111255		psap	15.0 kft	001	flow on
111311		bbr	15.0 kft	359	retract
111544		JW	15.0 kft	001	zero
111641		TW	15.0 kft	002	status ok
111815		heiman	15.0 kft	002	cal04
112802		bbr	15.0 kft	335	retract
113004		Video	15.0 kft	335	#1 ffc; #2 ufc start
113031		Video	15.0 kft	335	digital 4 views @ 1Hz
113834		temp	15.0 kft	334	checked ok
114239		gin	15.0 kft	319	track plot check ok
114539	120349	Profile 1	15.0 - -.16 kft	331	50ft
114731		bbr	13.2 kft	332	extend
120554		!	1.2 kft	163	manouvre
120608	122459	Run 1.1	1.3 kft	163	1020qnh 1500ft
122531		!	1.3 kft	089	manouvre
122601	122958	Profile 2	1.3 - -.19 kft	037	1022 qnh
122959	124140	Profile 3	-.19 - 5.2 kft	025	1022 qnh
123146		bbr	0.64 kft	033	retract
124340	125848	Run 2.1	2.3 kft	217	2500ft 1022
124727		JW	2.3 kft	216	zero
124823		nev	2.3 kft	216	zero
125008		heiman	2.3 kft	215	cal06
125909		!	2.3 kft	178	manouvre
125953	131549	Run 3	2.3 kft	117	
130258		Video	2.3 kft	123	#3 ffc; #4 ufc start
131755	134101	Run 4	2.3 kft	018	2500 ft 1022
134102	134631	Profile 4	2.3 - -.16 kft	015	2500 ft 1022 50ft
134648		!	0.01 kft	000	manouvre
134835	140047	Profile 5	-.16 - 4.9 kft	204	
135945		psap	4.5 kft	202	flow off
140108		!	4.4 kft	203	manouvre
140240	141418	Run 5	3.3 kft	203	
140402		psap	3.3 kft	202	flow on
141418	142132	Profile 6	3.3 - -.22 kft	209	
141545		P6	2.3 kft	209	interrupt
141602		!	2.2 kft	184	manouvre
141631		P6	2.3 kft	131	restart
142200		!	0.01 kft	144	manouvre
142355	142913	Profile 7	-.22 - 4.3 kft	332	
142822		psap	3.5 kft	330	flow off
142926		!	4.2 kft	329	manouvre
143115	144839	Run 6	2.2 kft	156	
143448		psap	2.2 kft	156	flow on
143636		Video	2.2 kft	155	#5 ffc; #6 ufc start
143717		heimann	2.2 kft	155	cal06
144903		!	2.2 kft	110	manouvre
144954	151127	Run 7	2.3 kft	016	
151242	153442	Run 8	2.2 kft	144	

153510		!	2.2 kft	201 manouvre
153531	155509	Run 9	2.3 - 2.2 kft	220
155705	160412	Profile 8	0.22 - 6.5 kft	283
160106		psap	3.9 kft	293 flow off
160206		psap	4.8 kft	291 flow on
160439	160450	Run 10	6.5 kft	295
160621		!	6.5 kft	287 end science
161922		heiman	6.5 kft	301 closed
161931		bbr	6.3 kft	300 extend
162722		Land	0.03 kft	214 Cranfield

B355 Track 02-APR-08

ADIENT Flight B355 - Shakedown and Calibration

Wednesday, April 2, 2008 –Crew list:

1. Captain – Al Foster (Direct Flight)
 2. First Officer – Ian Ramsay-Rae (Direct Flight)
 3. CCM – Gaynor Ottoway (Direct Flight)
 4. CCM2/Core Chemistry – Kate Turnbull (FAAM)
 5. Flight Manager – Ruth Purvis (FAAM)
 6. Cloud Physics – Phil Rosenberg (FAAM)
 7. Mission Scientist 1- Hugh Coe
 8. Mission Scientist 2 – Claire McConnell
 - ~~10. SWS/SHIMS – ?~~
 - ~~11. Wet Nephelometer/filters – (FAAM?)~~
 12. AMS 1 – (Manchester) **JAMES ALLEN**
 13. SP2 – (Manchester) **DANTONG LIU**
 14. **AMS 2 (Manchester) WILL MORGAN**
- FAAM sortie brief: Flight Number – B355, April 2, 2008**

Operating Area: D and E

Sortie Objectives: ADIENT initial flight for April/May period. Shakedown, calibrations, and some aerosol plume characterization work. Mission critical instruments: ToF-AMS, SP2

Weather: There is high pressure over the UK, with westerly winds leading to a build up of pollution over the North Sea from North England sources. Some scattered Sc predicted in the North Sea, especially along the SE coast of the UK.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Cranfield at 11z.
3. Transit at FL150 towards waypoint 76. [**60 min at transit speed**].
4. Descent profile at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft, aiming to finish profile at point 76. [**15 min, T=75**]
5. Ascend to 500ft, or an altitude within the aerosol layer (and avoiding low cloud where possible as determined by mission scientist). Suggested routing:
Waypoints 76-> 77->78->79->80->81->40-> 41->42->43
6. Where conditions are appropriate and cloud is at a minimum, (currently predicted to be just north of the Humber) profile down to 50 ft and perform broken profile ascent to FL100 or well above aerosol layers. As designated by the mission scientist perform either a series of stacked SLRs with profile ascents between, or a raster pattern within aerosol plumes.
7. Transit back to Cranfield at high level, science speed not necessary. [**30 min, T=270**]
8. Land Cranfield [**T=270**].
9. Perform pirouette as in step #1

Flight B355

2nd April 2008*Summary of the weather conditions:*

High pressure centred over Biscay brought brisk north westerly flow across much of the country. A weak front brought low cloud and light drizzle to much of south western Britain throughout the day. From the Kent coast northwards, shallow cumulus persisted and the skies were predominately cloud free over the North Sea. The NW flow led to pollution plumes from Edinburgh, Newcastle, Teeside, Hull, Leeds, Sheffield, Manchester to advect SE across the country and over the southern North Sea within a well defined boundary layer.

Points defined:

Point 76 (56°10'N 2°00'W) off St Abbs Head
and Point 41 (51°53'N 1°47'E) close to the Essex coast.

Summary of the flight:

A successful flight was carried out to test new instruments and to probe pollution plumes being advected from the east coast of the UK. The ToF-AMS had undergone some tests since its operation in Dec 2007 and these needed to be tested. The PCASP had not been operational since its comparison in Germany in March 2008 and the SP-2 instrument was undertaking its first mission on the FAAM aircraft. The

weather conditions provided an ideal opportunity to probe aerosol plumes downwind of the UK in clear, cloud free air over the coastal region of the North Sea. The flight plan was to transit to point 76 and then follow the coastal "AMPEP" waypoints south to point 41 before recovering to Cranfield. In addition, several cross wind legs were conducted at two altitudes in the boundary layer to investigate the plume structure. At the ends of these legs profiles were conducted to obtain vertical structure information. These crosswind legs were conducted as follows 1) south of Wearmouth in a NE direction at 2500', returning at 4000'; 2) from south of Flamborough Head in a NE direction at 2500', returning at 4000'; 3) from Blakeney Point in a NE direction at 2500'. In sufficient fuel was available for a return leg so the 2500' run was extended SE to provide a further cross wind run at 2500' towards the East Anglian coast. The aerosol was entirely within the boundary layer. There was considerable structure across the plumes and also vertically as it appeared that nitrate was present mostly close to the BL top. The scattering coefficients were between 25 and 50 Mm⁻¹. The whole of the

east coast showed enhancements in the aerosol load but individual plumes were clearly visible by eye at altitudes between 2500 and 4000' and could be identified by the scattering coefficient data and by the NO_x concentration enhancements of between 5 and 10 ppb. The pollution extended several tens of km offshore. The ToF-AMS and PCASP appeared to function satisfactorily. The SP-2 showed a reverse flow at altitude, though operated successfully at lower levels.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date 2/4/09 Name HUGH COE Page 1 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30Z					PRE T10 overcast 8/8 So WIND NE, ~5 m/s. SATELLITE FORECAST : CLEAR SKY OVER N SEA WIND NE FORECAST FOR CLEAR SLOT TO REMAIN THROUGH PM.
10:55Z					280° 14kts T=1°C. cloud 3500'
10:56Z	T10				Thin layer of Sc at 3500' with no extensive deck above second deck at 6600'. Cloud base ~ 8000'. Some scattered Stratus at mid level - little Ci.
11:29Z					low level Sc on transit north of some mid level altocumulus but little of same.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 355** Date 2/4/05 Name HUGH COE Page 2 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Cloud Gap off Flamborough Head.
11:35Z		FL150		334	SPZ reverse ykw at this level recog. will see if same at low level.
					AMS hi speed data collection checked - OK but switched to 30s.
11:45:39	P1	FL150 → 50ft	333	55°N 12°W	Profile descent to Layer 76. Only a few shallow scattered Cu in the region. No cloud of shoe at off Lindisfarne. Cu base at 6500' Moist above 700 mb - no aerosol above 5000 ft. T _d gra
					base at 3000 ft at base of BL 4 m ⁻¹ .
11:51:05		FL200			Descent Rate 500 ft / min at 2000 ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date 2/4/08 Name HUGH COE Page 3 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					SP2 started working in BL.
					AMS : 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ SO_2 , also OSS in BL.
12:06:08	R1	FL15	184°		Heading South to sample Pulse crossed $\approx 15 \text{ min}^{-1}$ NO_x sees peak at 2000' in descent.
					Heading to S of Newcastle profile down then through BL to just above the descent to obtain best.
12:24:10					Crossing Wearmouth.
12:24:54	edR1				
12:26:01	P2	FL150 $\rightarrow 50'$			Wind 310°
12:43:43	R2	FL250	215°		Problem crossing Edin plane. heading towards coast
12:50	R2				
Cross Section Crosswind NO_x off Newcastle.					

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date **2/4/08** Name **M. COS** Page **4** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:58:48	R2-1	2500ft	122°		end of cross wind run
					wind dir 297° 11-1s
	R3 2				heading down coasted
					run at 2500'
					This leg down the N. YORKSHIRE
					coast is almost downwind so
					along Middlesborough/
					Norse plane.
					Hdg 123° Wind 293°
					Seeing 3 ppt 100%; neph
					~ 20 m ⁻¹ .
					Run bent around Flamborough
					head. to capture Teeside
					plane then heading out
					on reciprocal cross wind.
13:16:40	R4	2500ft			'A' Start of run some
					scattered Cu.
13:21:50	R4	2500ft	150°		• heading offshore North East
					picking up a plane but
					vis layer thin and main layer
13:41:10	ad R4 stat R4	2500- 50ft @ 500'/min	150°		above.
					descent NE about and
					profile ascent

wind speed 8-1s sea state
have some white caps; up to now
calm.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date **2/4/08** Name **H. COE** Page **5** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:46:31	P4	end 30'			end P4
					turn to reciprocal and
					profile ascent.
13:48:35	P5	start 50'	323°		heading towards coast
					little bit of cloud at
					4700'.
					end climb at 5000 ft
14:00:45	P5	end.			descent to 3700'
					for return Flanburgh.
14:02:40	P5	3500'			
14:14:18	P6	↓ 50'			broken at 1416:02. to manoeuvre
14:21:32	P6				ended.
					turned into reciprocal heading
					N to profile up.
14:25:55	P7				
14:31:15	P6	2500'	following		close to Humber.
14:45:00	P6	2500'	coast → Blakeney.		Seeing large NO _x plume
					Here This looks like a
					clean air for particles;
					everything low.
14:48:39	end P6				at Blakeney
	P7				heading NE from Blakeney.
14:55					High NO ₂ seen by AMS
					no inc in SO ₂ ; O ₃ or neph
					but passing ngs ?!

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date 2/4/08 Name M. CCE Page 6 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:12:42	R7 end	2200			pos: headed out from
15:12:42	R8	2200	151		Blakeney Big Pine
					Close to Blakeney point
					but off shore clear.
					• No time for a return
					leg so R8 is heading
					S. SouthE (151°) and then
					cut across to Suffolk
					coast, another X wind
					leg.
15:30					Small Cu no sidespread above and
					to coast but still much
					clear sky say 2/8.
15:34:42	R8ad				close to point morix.
					clear air all ways down north
15:35:22	R9				Start of X wind leg towards
					Suffolk coast
15:37					Hit pine off E Anglia
					50Mm ¹ and 6 ppb
15:50:17	R9	2200	220	52°6'N 2°6'E	Wind 9ms ¹ 294°
					Cloud base much more
					extensive here.
					Heading to P41
					then descend to P41 at
					to 500' during turn and
					ascend to 6500' to recover
					here.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.355** Date **2/4/08** Name **M Coe** Page **7** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:55:07	end P9	2500	243		end of P9 descend to 3500ft
15:57:05	start P8	500'	283		start P9 for 500'.
16:02:10					- Dip in neph at 4000' near cloud top then peak just above cloud.
16:03:00					- In cloud briefly neph inc high.
16:06:00	end P8				end P8 and recover here end of science
					Extensive cloud over land, most aerosol must have been cloud processed, several level of stratiform cloud.
16:28:00					cloud top 5500' base 4500' cloud top 3000' base 1900' T/D

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 2/04/08	Operator: PDR	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:N/A	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time:N/A	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	352	0.08														FI030	
	95	0.09														FI035	
	78	0.08														FI045	
12:41:40	122	0.09														FI050 end profile 3	
12:43:49	84	0.11														FI023 start run 2.1	
12:46:00	12	0.1															
12:48:00	400	0.08															
12:50:00	357	0.09															
12:52:00	258	0.09															
12:54:00	224	0.09															
12:56:00	178	0.09															
12:58:00	307	0.09															
12:58:48	297	0.09														End run 2.1	
12:59:53	359	0.08														Start run 3	
13:03:00	323	0.09															
13:05:00	340	0.09															
13:08:00	355	0.09															
13:10:00	296	0.11															
13:11:00	418	0.09															
13:13:00	472	0.1															
13:15:49	728	0.09														End run 3	
13:17:55	708	0.09														Start run 4 fI022	
13:20:00	465	0.1															
13:26:00	300	0.1															
13:28:00	211	0.1															
13:30:00	283	0.1															
13:32:00	134	0.09															
13:35:00	168	0.09															
13:38:00	132	0.09															
13:41:00	120	0.09														End run 4 startprofile 4 fI022	
	151	0.09														FI015	
	138	0.08														FI010	
	184	0.1														FI005	
13:46:31	153	0.1														50 ft end profile 4	
13:48:35	194	0.1														50 ft start profile 5	
	115	0.09														FI006	
	120	0.09														FI010	
	145	0.09														FI015	
	108	0.09														FI020	
	183	0.09	1237													FI030	
	313	0.1														FI040	
14:00:47	105	0.08														FI048 end profile 5	
14:02:40	174	0.1														FI033 start run 6	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.2	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =N/A	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =N/A
PCASP Flow rate =0.78		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =N/A	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =N/A	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =2		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 2/04/08	Operator: PDR	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:N/A	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	Aux1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time:N/A	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
						Sorry no log due to sorting SID											
14:13:00	887	0.09															
14:14:40	347	0.1														End run 6 start profile 6	
	418	0.09														FI025	
	402	0.09														FI015	
	360	0.09														FI005	
14:21:32	240	0.09														50 ft end profile 6	
14:23:55	281	0.09														50 ft atart profile 7	
	260	0.1														FI010	
	231	0.1														FI020	
	310	0.09														FI030	
	228	0.08														FI040 end profile 7	
14:36:00	279	0.1															
14:39:00	361	0.1															
14:41:00	405	0.09															
14:44:00	438	0.1															
14:46:00	468	0.12															
14:48:00	947	0.11															
14:48:39	885	0.11														End run 6	
	487	0.12														Start run 7	
14:52:00	573	0.1															
14:54:00	408	0.11															
15:02:00	200	0.1															
15:06:00																Blip as turned pcasp off by mistake instead of SID	
15:09:00	160	0.09															
15:11:00	111	0.1															
15:11:27	157	0.09														End run 7	
15:12:42	175	0.09														Start run 8	
15:15:00	165	0.09															
15:17:30	184	0.09															
15:19:00	217	0.09															
15:21:00	147	0.09															
15:23:00	154	0.09															
15:25:00	177	0.1															
15:27:00	183	0.09															
15:29:00	204	0.08															
15:31:00	300	0.1															
15:33:00	124	0.09															
15:34:52	168	0.1														End run 8	
15:35:31	141	0.1														Start run 9	
15:39:00	177	0.1															
15:41:00	124	0.1															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.2	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.2	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1.2	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =N/A	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =N/A
PCASP Flow rate =0.78		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =1	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =N/A	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =N/A
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =N/A	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =2		

Flight:

B355

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B355

Date: 2 April 2008

Instruments

1. TW required power cycling to set status ok
2. Deiced & non deiced ok – 0.5k split, deiced cold
3. neph ok
4. AMTG screen crash at 13:43
5. SID producing vast data files
- 6.

Aircraft

1. cloud physics reports ssp intercom box not working.
- 2.

ISDN Emails

2 attempts to connect – both successful but outbox message not sent, no incoming messages

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

B355 neph lat all.jpg

B355 P1 neph.jpg

B355 neph time all.jpg

B355 P1 nox.jpg

B355 P1 tephigram.jpg

B355 P3 nox newcastle.jpg

B355 P3 neph newcastle.jpg

B355 P3 tephigram newcastle.jpg

B355 P4-5 neph offshore yorkshire.jpg

B355 P6-7 neph.jpg

B355 P4-5 teph offshore yorkshire.jpg

B355 P6-7 tephigram.jpg

B355 P8 all tephigram.jpg

B355 P8 off essex coast NOx.jpg

B355 P8 off essex coast neph.jpg

B355 R1 cn northumberland.jpg

B355 R1 co northumberland.jpg

B355 R2-1 neph newcastle out and back.jpg

B355 R1 neph northumberland.jpg

B355 R2-1 nox newcastle out and back.jpg

B355 R8 and R9 E Anglia neph.jpg

B355 trackplot all.jpg

B355 track plot end P7.jpg

R4 neph off york coast time series.jpg

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B355:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	No log has been made available yet.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
SP2 log	SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Oct 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_113101_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_123108_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_123101_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_133101_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_143101_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080402_r0_b355_153101_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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